

FERROMAGNETIC MICROWIRES AND THEIR MULTIFUNCTIONAL POLYMER COMPOSITES

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The last two decades have witnessed intensive studies on the ferromagnetic microwires worldwide. Recent attention has turned to the development of innovative materials and composites derived from these microwires, such as microwire polymer composites. Through incorporating even extremely low concentration of microwires ($\sim 10^{-2}$ vol.%), the resultant composite exhibits a multitude of functionalities which are desirable for a range of technological applications. This talk samples several case studies of the ongoing research on microwire composites from synthesis to structural and property evaluation with a focus on the multi-functionalities presented in these microwire-composites. Starting with an introduction of multifunctional composites and the theories pertinent to the multiple functionalities of microwire composites, a detailed description of fabrication methods of microwire composites is given with a comparison of different processing techniques. Two fundamental effects, namely, giant magnetoimpedance (GMI) and stress-impedance (GSI) effects of microwire composites are discussed in relative to the monolithic microwires. Microwave tunable properties and associated peculiarities of electromagnetic spectra are analysed in the presence of low (of 30Oe) and high magnetic field (up to 1kOe) and stress field. The ferromagnetic wire composites have also been shown to possess metamaterial characteristics and microwave absorption capability. With a discussion on the underlying physics of the influence of composite architecture such as material parameters of microwires and microwire periodicity on the performance of resultant composites, useful insights are provided for an effective design of smart

composites for specific engineering applications such as structural health monitoring, stress sensing, invisible cloaking, microwave absorption applications.

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